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Strengthening Communicable Disease surveillance through a simplified complementary digital dashboard at Colombo Regional Director of Health Services

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Background: A complementary dashboard to monitor the timeliness of surveillance of Communicable Diseases requiring special investigation, Dengue, Tuberculosis and Leprosy.

Description of the intervention: To enhance the timely field investigations, a dashboard was developed at the Colombo Regional Director of Health Services (RDHS) for each Medical Officer of Health (MOH) areas. The dashboard covered the entities of twelve diseases requiring special investigations, along with dengue, tuberculosis and leprosy – all of which has a higher disease burden in Colombo. Individual level data are available for leprosy and tuberculosis with mutual data entry from district and MOH level. This facilitated contact tracing as well. The coverage and timeliness of diseases requiring special investigations as well as the percentage of outcomes entered by MOH area for dengue. These are complementary to the electronic data systems of national level institutions.

Methods used for the evaluation: Performance was evaluated by tracking the timeliness of investigations, completeness of forms and dengue outcome entries. Regular feedback was provided to MOHs based on these indicators.

Results: The dashboard significantly enhanced monitoring and management of cases, allowing real-time issue detection and prompt response, while also reducing the administrative burden at both district and MOH levels. The timeliness of SI form submissions has reached 100%. TB and leprosy records are now uniformly monitored at both ends. Additionally, dengue outcome data entry improved from 43.3% in early February to 86.6% by the end of March 2025.

Lessons learnt: Low cost simplified digital dashboards that enabled monitoring of selected aspects complementary to the national e-platforms enables increasing timeliness and coordination of events at district and MOH level.

Key words: Communicable Disease surveillance, Dengue, Tuberculosis, Leprosy,

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